

Studies on Biologically Relevant Binary and Ternary Metal Chelates. Ternary Copper(II), Nickel(II), Zinc(II) and Cadmium(II) Chelates with 2,2'-Bipyridylamine and Bidentate Amino Acids and Tridentate Aspartic Acid^ψ

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The study of ternary complexes involving an aromatic amine as the primary ligand (A), a metal ion and various biomolecules as secondary ligands (L) can serve as useful model to understand complex formation and biochemical reactions. In the present investigation, we report the coordination of a series of bidentate amino acids and aspartic acid with 2,2'-bipyridylamine (A) bound Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} or Cd^{II}. Formation constants for the following equilibria have been evaluated,

Results and Discussion

In the ternary systems involving a 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio of M(II), 2,2'-bipyridylamine and amino acids, the titration curves exhibit a single step inflexion at $m = 5$ except aspartic acid. Representative potentiometric titration curve (at 25°) for the 1 : 1 : 1 ternary system involving Cu^{II}-2,2'-bipyridylamine-glycine is given in Fig. 1. Although the mono- and bis-formation constants were reported earlier¹, the results obtained in the present investigation are in good agreement with the previously reported values. The relative stabilities of the ternary complexes compared to the corresponding binary

Fig. 1. Cu^{II}-2,2'-bipyridylamine-glycine system at 25° : (1) acid, (2) 2,2'-bipyridylamine, (3) glycine, (4) 1 : 1 molar ratio of Cu^{II} + 2,2'-bipyridylamine and (5) 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio of Cu^{II} + 2,2'-bipyridylamine glycine.

complexes can be qualitatively expressed in many

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different ways. We have expressed the relative stabilities in terms of $\Delta \log K$,

$$\Delta \log K_B = \log K_{ML_2}^{ML} - \log K_{ML}^M \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta \log K_T = \log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M \quad (5)$$

The advantage of using $\Delta \log K$ for comparison of the stability of binary and ternary complexes has been reviewed². The $\log K_{ML}^M$, $\log K_{ML_2}^{ML}$, $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$, $\Delta \log K_B$ and $\Delta \log K_T$ values obtained in the present investigation are presented in Tables 1-3.

Studies on ternary systems containing 2,2'-bipyridylamine as the primary ligand (A) show that in the presence of an aromatic nitrogen donor, metal ions become more selective and discriminate between the donor groups on the incoming³ secondary

ligand. $[M(A)]^{2+}$ binds secondary ligand with an ionic oxygen donor (O⁻-O⁻) much more firmly than ligands with nitrogen donor (N-N). The affinity for ligands with N and O donors (N-O⁻) lies between pure O⁻-O⁻ and N-N ligands.

The $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ values are found to be higher than $\log K_{ML_2}^{ML}$ and are lower than $\log K_{ML}^M$. The order of formation constants for the ternary complexes is the same as that for the binary ML complexes⁴. All the metals obey Irving-William order. The $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ values follow the order : glycine \geq α -alanine \approx leucine \geq isoleucine $>$ valine, serine \approx threonine \approx methionine $<$ aspartic acid $>$ phenylalanine. The sequence is explained in terms of ligands structures and basicities. Higher values of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ originate from the back-donating tendency of the primary ligand, besides the N \rightarrow M σ -bonding

TABLE 1-DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF FREE LIGANDS AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE BINARY M(II) AMINO ACID COMPLEXES*

Ligand (L)	pK ₁ ^H	pK ₂ ^H	logK _{Cu} ^{Cu}	logK _{CuL} ^{CuL}	logK _{NiL} ^{Ni}	logK _{NiL₂} ^{NiL}	logK _{ZnL} ^{Zn}	logK _{ZnL₂} ^{ZnL}	logK _{CdL} ^{Cd}	logK _{CdL₂} ^{CdL}
Glycine	9.60	2.31	8.11	6.67	5.90	5.05	5.22	4.37	4.24	3.69
α -Alanine	9.76	2.31	8.21	6.84	5.55	4.53	5.17	4.10	4.27	3.46
Leucine	9.67	2.33	8.58	7.29	5.54	4.55	4.74	4.36	4.92	3.56
Isoleucine	9.70	2.31	8.49	7.52	5.43	4.49	4.88	4.33	3.91	3.37
Valine	9.60	2.31	8.91	7.32	5.48	4.42	4.74	4.24	3.91	3.22
Serine	9.09	2.16	8.33	6.96	5.69	4.76	5.06	4.11	3.95	3.30
Threonine	9.05	2.17	8.09	7.23	5.96	4.93	5.16	4.19	4.02	3.20
Methionine	9.14	2.18	8.23	7.25	5.60	4.18	4.69	3.96	4.30	4.04
Aspartic acid	9.60	3.60	8.57	6.98	7.17	5.32	5.74	4.09	4.53	3.50
Phenylalanine	8.80	2.20	7.70	6.75	5.20	4.62	4.70	3.72	3.88	3.15

*Constant values accurate to ± 0.02 units.

TABLE 2-STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR TERNARY Cu^{II} AND Ni^{II} COMPLEXES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES*

Ligand (L)	25°		35°		45°		25°		35°		45°	
	logK _{CuAL} ^{CuA}	$\Delta \log K_T$	logK _{CuAL} ^{CuA}	$\Delta \log K_T$	logK _{CuAL} ^{CuA}	$\Delta \log K_T$	logK _{NiAL} ^{NiA}	$\Delta \log K_T$	logK _{NiAL} ^{NiA}	$\Delta \log K_T$	logK _{NiAL} ^{NiA}	$\Delta \log K_T$
Glycine	7.80	-0.31	7.27	-0.84	7.14	-0.97	5.48	-0.42	5.40	-0.50	5.30	-0.60
α -Alanine	7.88	-0.33	7.57	-0.64	7.84	-0.73	5.28	-0.27	5.17	-0.38	5.10	-0.45
Leucine	7.99	-0.59	7.73	-0.85	7.41	-1.17	5.38	-0.16	5.21	-0.33	4.94	-0.60
Isoleucine	7.36	-1.13	7.60	-0.89	7.31	-1.18	5.09	-0.34	4.91	-0.52	4.79	-0.64
Valine	7.71	-1.20	7.29	-1.62	7.23	-1.68	4.90	-0.58	4.79	-0.69	4.68	-0.80
Serine	7.41	-0.92	7.21	-1.12	7.10	-1.23	5.20	-0.49	4.88	-0.81	4.72	-0.97
Threonine	8.11	-0.02	7.13	-0.96	6.83	-1.26	5.34	-0.62	5.18	-0.78	4.97	-0.99
Methionine	7.70	-0.53	7.17	-1.06	7.73	-0.50	5.38	-0.22	5.00	-0.60	4.71	-0.89
Aspartic acid	8.63	+0.06	7.92	-0.65	7.62	-0.95	6.75	-0.37	6.41	-0.71	6.18	-0.94
Phenylalanine	7.90	+0.20	7.70	0.00	7.55	-0.15	4.92	-0.28	4.62	-0.58	4.46	-0.74

*Constant values accurate to ± 0.02 units in all the systems; $\Delta \log K_T = (\log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M)$, A = 2,2'-bipyridylamine.

TABLE 3—STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR TERNARY Zn^{II} and Cd^{II} COMPLEXES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES* $\mu = 0.2 M (NaClO_4)$

Ligand (L)	25°		35°		45°		25°		35°		45°	
	$\log K_{ZnAL}^{ZnA}$	$\Delta \log K_T$	$\log K_{ZnAl}^{ZnA}$	$\Delta \log K_T$	$\log K_{ZnAL}^{ZnA}$	$\Delta \log K_T$	$\log K_{CdAL}^{CdA}$	$\Delta \log K_T$	$\log K_{CdAL}^{CdA}$	$\Delta \log K_T$	$\log K_{CdAL}^{CdA}$	$\Delta \log K_T$
Glycine	5.04	-0.18	4.80	-0.42	4.72	-0.50	4.20	-0.04	4.08	-0.16	3.69	-0.55
α -Alanine	4.92	-0.25	4.73	-0.44	4.60	-0.57	4.15	-0.12	3.99	-0.28	3.69	-0.58
Leucine	4.69	-0.05	4.53	-0.21	4.30	-0.44	4.18	-0.74	3.94	-0.98	3.74	-1.18
Isoleucine	4.81	-0.07	4.61	-0.27	4.49	-0.39	3.91	-0.01	3.75	-0.16	3.53	-0.38
Valine	4.63	-0.11	4.56	-0.18	4.41	-0.33	3.88	-0.03	3.67	-0.24	3.49	-0.42
Serine	4.71	-0.35	4.72	-0.34	4.45	-0.61	3.76	-0.19	3.65	-0.30	3.46	-0.49
Threonine	4.85	-0.31	4.79	-0.37	4.60	-0.56	3.72	-0.30	3.55	-0.47	3.34	-0.68
Methionine	4.54	-0.15	4.23	-0.46	4.10	-0.59	3.85	-0.45	3.22	-1.08	3.06	-1.24
Aspartic acid	5.52	-0.22	5.43	-0.31	5.12	-0.62	4.51	-0.02	4.22	-0.31	3.96	-0.57
Phenyl alanine	4.45	-0.25	4.30	-0.40	4.13	-0.57	3.65	-0.23	3.52	-0.36	3.31	-0.57

Explanation same as in Table 2.

there exist strong $M \rightarrow N$ π -interaction. As a result, the concentration of electrons does not increase significantly on the metal ion. In other words, positive charge on the metal ion in $[MA]^{2+}$ is almost the same as in $[M(aq)]^{2+}$ complexes. The observed formation constant values indicate similar nature of 2,2'-bipyridylamine and 2,2'-bipyridyl. In all the binary complexes, $\Delta \log K_B$ values are negative. It is more negative in case of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} . In all the ternary complexes of amino acids, the $\Delta \log K_T$ values are negative, except Cu.A. aspartic acid and phenyl alanine systems. The secondary ligands have long enough sidechain to hydrophobically interact with one of the pyridine rings of 2,2'-bipyridylamine. This intramolecular hydrophobic interaction in such complexes may lead to the modest increase in the stability of ternary complexes. The effective basicity of aspartate ion is higher, hence it forms more stable complexes.

Experimental

The amino acids glycine, α -alanine, leucine, isoleucine, valine, threonine, aspartic acid (all AnalaR), methionine (Loba), perchloric acid and sodium hydroxide (E. Merck) and sodium perchlorate (Fluka) were used.

Stock solutions of metal perchlorates were prepared and standardised by titrating against EDTA⁵. Carbonate-free NaOH (Fluka) solution was standardised with potassium hydrogen phthalate⁶. Dou-

ble-distilled water was used throughout the work. The formation constants of binary and ternary metal complexes were determined by potentiometric titration⁷ of various ligands with standard carbonate-free NaOH in the presence and absence of metal. An identical condition was maintained in binary and ternary systems. For the mixed ligand complex formation to take place in steps, the two ligands should combine with the metal ion in two different pH ranges. The complex formation of MA should be complete in the lower pH range and it should be stable in the region where combination of the secondary ligand takes place⁴. In such systems the solution consists of species MA, MAL and also MAL_2 , if there is an excess of ligand L. This presumes that MA does not undergo hydrolysis or hydroxy complex formation in the range where the combination of ligand L takes place. Therefore, 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio of MAL was employed for ternary systems. All the titrations were carried out at different temperatures in the inert atmosphere of nitrogen. The pH measurements were carried out with an Elico LI-10-T pH meter fitted with a combination glass electrode assembly.

The successive acid dissociation constants pK_1^H and pK_2^H were calculated using equations (6) and (7),

$$pK_2^H = \frac{[H^+] [(a-1)T_L + (H^+) - (OH^-)]}{T_L - [(a-1) T_L + (H^+) (OH^-)]} \quad (6)$$

$$pK_1^H = \frac{[H^+] [aT_L + (H^+) - (OH^-)]}{T_L [aT_L + (H^+) - (OH^-)]} \quad (7)$$

where, a is the moles of base added per mole of ligand and T_L the total concentration of the ligand species.

The stability constants of binary mono (1 : 1) and bis (1 : 2) M(II)-amino acid complexes were calculated from the potentiometric titration data using Rossotti-Rossotti technique⁷. The formation constants of ternary systems were calculated using equation (8),

$$K_{MAL}^{MA} = \frac{[MAL]}{[MA] [L]} \quad (8)$$

Precise values of ternary constants were determined by the method of averages⁸.

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References

1. M. V. CHIDAMBARAM, Ph. D. Thesis, M. S. University of Baroda, 1971.
2. R. B. MARTIN and R. PRADOS, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 1665.
3. M. S. MOHAN, D. BANCROFT and E. H. ABBOTT, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1979, **18**, 344; C. F. CONDIKE and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 2455; M. S. MOHAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 252.
4. M. PHILIP, M. N. PATEL, M. P. PEERZADA and J. D. JOSHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **65**, 871.
5. H. A. FLASHKA, "EDTA Titrations", Pergman, Oxford, 1964.
6. G. SCHWARZENBACH and R. BIEDERRNANN, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1948, **31**, 331.
7. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904; I. P. MAVANI, C. R. JEJURKAR and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 469.
8. S. N. DUBEY and R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **47**, 881.